

STUDENTS' EXPERIENCES ON VERBAL PUNISHMENTS: PERCEIVED INFLUENCE IN STUDENTS' SCIENCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

In today's time, the mental well-being of undergraduate students is a pressing concern that stems from many possible reasons, verbal punishment being one. This study explored the perceived influence of verbal punishment on students' science learning. Using a mixed-methods approach, the researchers collected quantitative and qualitative data from 133 students. Quantitative analysis by using means revealed that students experienced various forms of verbal punishment, including accusation, name-calling, shaming, belittling, and reprimanding. While freshmen and seniors reported minimal exposure, sophomores and juniors experienced these punishments more frequently. Qualitative data analysis using thematic analysis uncovered both positive and negative consequences of verbal punishment. Some students reported increased independence, while others experienced demotivation. These findings contribute to a growing body of research on the complex effects of verbal punishment. Future studies should examine the prevalence and long-term consequences of this behavior in educational settings.

Keywords: *Mental Well-Being, Science Learning, Verbal Punishment*

INTRODUCTION

Verbal punishment is considered by Wang and Li (2020) as a form of psychological abuse that involves negative speech and can cause distress and harm to the offender's mental health. Studies have shown that verbal abuse can result in elevated loneliness and a decline in maintaining social relationships. Most students are unaware of their abuse and do not report it to anyone, leading to increased acts against them. Verbal punishment can also affect students' learning, creating a hostile environment that is not conducive to learning.

Students often face unconcerned teachers and authoritative behaviors, which promote disinterest in learning rather than motivation. Research has shown that emotional abuse can significantly influence students' academic achievement, leading to depression and lack of concentration. On the other hand, verbal punishment can also be a catalyst for transformative learning, as it can make a child feel worthless and incapable.

While many studies have reported negative perceptions of verbal punishment, there is a lack of rigorous research on its positive influence on students. The current study aims to determine the perceived influence of verbal punishment on students' science learning, focusing not only on its negative influence but also its positive influence. This research will help to address the lack of research on the positive influence of verbal punishment on students' well-being and academic performance.

Research Questions

This study investigated the perceived influence of verbal punishment on college students' science learning, and answered the following questions:

1. What are the different types of verbal punishments experienced by college students inside a science classroom?
2. How frequent do college students experience verbal punishments inside a science classroom?
3. How frequent does every year level experience different types of verbal punishments?
4. What is the perceived influence of verbal punishment on students with regards to their science learning?

METHODOLOGY

The participants were College Students that are aged 18- 25 years old, and residing in the National Capital Region, and fifteen (15) students were chosen from each year level. The participants were chosen using random sampling, and there were 133 participants in this research. The participants who were chosen for the individual interview were selected via purposive sampling based on their response on the Verbal Punishment Scale, and their consent to participate in the Verbal Punishment Interview Protocol.

The researchers used a Mixed Method Embedded Design. A Mixed Method Embedded Design is defined as a mixed method design wherein one data set is needed to support the succeeding data set. This design includes the collection of quantitative and qualitative data. However, one of the data serves as a supplement to the other set of data (Creswell, 2012). Embedded Design can use either a one-phase or a two-phase approach for the embedded data. The quantitative and qualitative data were used to answer different research questions within the study (Hanson et al., 2005).

Verbal Punishment Scale (VPS) was adapted from Babu et al. (2015) to collect quantitative data to measure the frequency of verbal abuse among students. It is a 14-item questionnaire with a four-point response scale with higher scores indicating greater levels of exposure to the seven (7) types of verbal punishment.

Verbal Punishment Interview Protocol (VIP) was used by the researchers to gather qualitative data about the students' experiences with regards to the perceived influence of verbal punishment on their science learning. The researchers adapted the interview questions from Roth (2004). The researchers also used a web-based individual interview. The interview consists of eight (8) open-ended questions that assess perceived influence of verbal punishment on students' science learning.

Before conducting the research, the researchers chose the National Capital Region as their research site with 133 college students aged 18 to 25 years old, and fifteen (15) students were chosen from each year level for the interview. Each respondent was given a consent form that invited them to participate in the researchers' study. In the form, essential information about the study was indicated such as the profile of the researchers, purpose of the study, procedure of the research, confidentiality, and consent to participate.

The researchers measured the frequency of verbal punishment by constructing the Verbal Punishment Scale that was adapted from Babu et al. (2015). The researchers then created a Google Form that contained the details of the research explaining its purpose, procedures, and contact information of the researchers. It also included the VPS that was made up of 14 questions with a four-point response scale for the students to answer. Each item in the VPS corresponds to the seven (7) types of verbal punishment based on the review of related literature. The researchers then disseminated the created Google Form to the participants, and their responses were collected by the researchers for analysis, and interpretation.

Interview was conducted using the Verbal Punishment Interview Protocol to collect data about the perceived influence of verbal punishment on students' science learning. The researchers informed the students about a scheduled Google/Zoom Meeting ahead of time. Before the interview, the researchers asked for the students' permission to record the session for the transcription of the interview. During the interview, the researchers asked the students with the eight (8) open-ended questions. Finally, after the interview, the researchers collected, analyzed, and interpreted the data with the use of thematic analysis.

Descriptive statistics were used to identify the prevalent types of verbal punishment experienced by college students. The frequency of verbal punishment experienced by students from their teachers was also analyzed using Descriptive Statistics. Lastly, thematic analysis was used to analyze the interviews, transcribe the responses of the participants, and identify the perceived influence of verbal punishment on students' science learning.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Different Types of Verbal Punishment Experienced by Students

In the Verbal Punishment Scale, each two items in the survey instrument corresponded to different types of verbal punishment namely *Accusation, Name-Calling, Blaming, Reprimanding, Shaming, Belittling, and Humiliation*. Among these, college students experienced all the types of verbal punishment except blaming and humiliation. In Table 1, it is shown that items 9-10 and items 13-14 have a mean of 1.47 and 1.38 respectively. Based on the instrument scale, both would have an interpretation of never and zero (0) times per week.

Table 1.

Survey Items and Means

Corresponding Type of Verbal Punishment	Item Number	Mean
Accusation	1	1.53
	2	1.50
	3	1.50
Name-calling	4	1.75
	5	1.58
Shaming	6	1.50
	7	1.78
Belittling	8	1.70
	9	1.58
Blaming		

	10	1.35
	11	1.47
Reprimanding	12	1.60
	13	1.40
Humiliation	14	1.35

Note. Mean from each item indicates that the students experienced verbal punishment.

The items correspond to the study of Adeogun, and Arigbo (2018) wherein they mentioned in their study that the usual types of verbal punishments experienced by students are name-calling, shaming, and belittling. However, the researchers in the present study found out that they experienced accusation, and reprimanding, as well.

The researchers found out that students' experience accusation because their teacher assumes that they are cheating due to having a good score in a test. Just like what Eriyanti (2018) stated in his study, the teacher accused the student of being inconsistent since the answer was always the same as the others.

For name-calling, the students experience it because of their gender preference that could be easily noticed by the teachers. This is in line with the study of Anderssen et al. (2015), where they have mentioned that one reason that words relating to sexual orientation, such as gay, faggot, lezzie, and so forth, are widely used in name-calling is probably that people perceive it as negative to be called these names. The researchers also found out that students' experience shaming due to professional differences between the student and the teacher as the teacher wanted to prove that their knowledge is more advanced compared to the student's knowledge.

In the study of Buisson et al. (2018), they have mentioned that the mistreatment coming from the teachers is due to asserting their professional competence to students. Moreover, students experience belittling due to their poor performance in class compared to other higher performing classmates in class. They are belittled because they score lower than their other classmates. This could be proved by the study of Bahou and Zakharia (2019) where they stated that one reason for violent discipline is having low grades.

As for reprimanding, the students experienced it because of their reluctance to answer and participate in the recitation. The silence brought about by not participating in the recitation can be disruptive in the sense that the flow of discussion is interrupted. Calderella et al. (2020) stated that one reason for reprimanding is because teachers are more focused on reprimanding students that are disruptive to the classroom learning environment.

Blaming and humiliation were never experienced by the students. In the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, it is stated in Article VIII- *“The Teachers and Learners”* that a teacher shall not inflict any forms of punishment upon the learner as a punishment for their actions (Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers Explained, 2019).

However, its implementation cannot be assured to have reached its full effect. One possible reason was mentioned by a K-12 physical education educator from the study of Jones (2017) where the teacher admitted that her knowledge of education law was inadequate, and that she had limited knowledge of laws that governed the profession. In her own words, she stated *“I have to admit that it is a form of negligence.”*

Frequency of Verbal Punishment in the Science Classroom

Table 2 shows that students experienced *accusation, name-calling, shaming, belittling, and reprimanding* as sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week. *Blaming* and *humiliation* was almost never or zero (0) times per week. The average of all verbal punishments is 1.53 which means sometimes.

Table 2

Mean and Interpretation of Each Type of Verbal Punishment

Type of Verbal Punishment	Mean	Interpretation
Accusation	1.52	Sometimes (1-2 times per week)
Name-calling	1.54	Sometimes (1-2 times per week)
Shaming	1.54	Sometimes (1-2 times per week)
Belittling	1.74	Sometimes (1-2 times per week)
Blaming	1.47	Never (0 times per week)
Reprimanding	1.53	Sometimes (1-2 times per week)
Humiliation	1.38	Never (0 times per week)

Average

1.53

Sometimes (1-2 times
per week)

The college students experienced verbal punishment usually at frequency of sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week. It is similar to the study of Thomason (2018) in which 73 respondents who responded “yes” to being verbally abused, 39 of them experienced verbal punishment once a week, and 24 of them were exposed to verbal abuse at least once a month. These would only show that verbal punishment is evident and occurring inside the classroom.

Students experience accusation, name-calling, belittling, shaming and reprimanding sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week equally due to the quality of work they produce, and how they perform, and behave in class. Some experience accusations due to the submitted written works being similar with the work of others. This could be seen in the study of Eriyanti (2018), where the teacher accused the student of being inconsistent since the answer was always the same as the others. Moreover, Cullinan et al. (2021) mentioned that most students who experience slow internet connection were students who belong to low-income families, and this may be the reason why students could be reprimanded, belittled, and shamed due to poor internet signals, and inability to respond quickly to the questions posted by the teacher during class. This results in students’ submission of school works with poor quality. Thus, they were given a moniker/nickname for those instances.

In the case of blaming and humiliation, students experienced it equally never or zero times per week. One possible reason is that physical and humiliating punishments are prohibited in the classroom (Alampay et al., 2017). Also, the DepEd Order no. 40 s.2012 or the DepEd Child Protection Policy was enacted for the protection of the student, and such acts like humiliating and blaming students could be punishable by law. Another possible reason is that students are most likely to be placed in groups for their activities, and this in turn lessens the possibility of individual blaming and humiliation.

Frequency of Different Verbal Punishments Experienced by Every Year Level

In Table 3, the frequency of each type of verbal punishment per year level is shown. Freshman students experienced all the different types of verbal punishment never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.24. The Sophomores experienced name-calling, shaming, belittling, blaming, and reprimanding sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week and accusation and humiliation never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.59. For the Juniors, they experienced Verbal Punishment experienced accusation, shaming, and belittling, blaming and reprimanding sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week and name-calling, blaming, reprimanding and humiliation never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.47. Lastly, the Seniors experienced all the different types of verbal punishment never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.33.

Table 3*Frequency and Interpretation of Verbal Punishment in Each Year Level*

Type of Verbal Punishment	Frequency			
	Freshman	Sophomore	Junior	Senior
Accusation	1.37	1.43	1.57	1.35
Name-calling	1.16	1.54	1.47	1.38
Shaming	1.32	1.67	1.53	1.37
Belittling	1.32	1.89	1.66	1.37
Blaming	1.16	1.52	1.49	1.26
Reprimanding	1.13	1.67	1.28	1.46
Humiliation	1.21	1.41	1.27	1.11
Average	1.24	1.59	1.47	1.33

Note: Always (5 or more times per week), 3 = Often (3-4 times per week), 2 = Sometimes (1-2 times per week), 1= Never (0 times per week)

After analyzing the average of the frequency of verbal punishment experienced per year level, the researchers ranked them into four (4) with the Sophomores having ranked 1, Juniors in rank 2, Seniors in rank 3 and Freshmen in rank 4.

The reason why Sophomores and Juniors ranked first and second respectively is due to the number of science courses they have. In the Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) 75 Series of 2017, there are 73 units of science courses. Majority of these are taken during the sophomore and junior years. First year students usually have general education courses while the seniors take the on-the-job training course which limit exposure to science courses. Another possible reason as to why freshmen got the lowest rank to experience verbal punishment was mentioned by Alipio (2020) wherein he reported in his study that freshmen adjust to college often in terms of institutional attachment, which leads them to follow the rules of the school.

Furthermore, Seniors are more likely to follow the rules to increase chances of graduating. Higher Education Institutions (HEI) can implement disciplinary rules dealing with misconduct (CHED, 2013). Seniors are aiming to graduate without any offenses that might hinder their intention to finish their academic program. Failure to do so such as

display of gross disrespect or discourtesy in any form towards any member of the university community may result in suspension, or worse, expulsion.

Perceived Influence of Verbal Punishment to Students' Science Learning

In the present study, students had mentioned that they had a positive perceived influence of verbal punishment to their science learning. As shown in Table 4, they indicated that the verbal punishments they experienced encouraged them to do better, it became an opportunity for self-improvement, led them to be dependent on themselves, and using it as a driving factor to change the teacher's perspective towards them.

Table 4

Positive Perceived Influence of Verbal Punishment

Themes	Subthemes	Students' Response
It became an opportunity for Self-Improvement	Taking Initiative	"I created a Google Doc, like we all made notes on that subject together so that he would have nothing else to say to us." (Rain)
	Ideation to adjust for the sake of the class	"At that time, I thought, I need to catch up with them. I need to keep up with their pace because if they adjust to me, we will really be delayed." (Katropa)
Becoming Self-Dependent	Adapting to the situation	"I became more aware of the factors that make them do that, and what I should do in those situations. It's like I 'adapted'." (Senyorpickels)
	Being responsible for own learning	"The positive is I was able to study on my own more, and read textbooks, as well as ask others, not relying solely on the professor's explanation." (Lei)
Using verbal punishment as a driving factor to	Took verbal punishment as a challenge	"I want to prove that I'm not like that, that I am more than that." (Rain)

change teacher's perspective to the students	Having an " <i>I am more than what you think</i> " mindset	"It fueled me to prove myself more that 'You can't doubt me, I know my capabilities'." (Ariel)
Encourages an individual to be better	Using verbal punishment as a reminder to be better	"In a way, when the verbal punishments from my teachers really sunk in, I actually used it as motivation to strive harder in my science studies." (Borbs)
	Using verbal punishment to strive harder	"I tried harder." (LJ)

According to Li and Zhang (2020), a teacher's language violence sometimes has a positive impact on students. Though it was rarely mentioned in their study's interview, they reported that it exists objectively. In their study, they stated that it is because the verbal violence of their teachers is a factor to motivate themselves, and this is a match to the response of Rain in which he mentioned that "*I created a Google Doc, like we all made notes on that subject together so that he would have nothing else to say to us.*"

Moreover, some students in their study indicated that they experienced verbal punishment because their teacher wants them to do better. One student had mentioned "*Sometimes the teacher would say things, but that's because the teacher wanted us to improve.*" which is in line with the response of Senyorpickels when he said "*I became more aware of the factors that make them do that, and what I should do in those situations. It's like I 'adapted'.*" which encouraged him to do better by means of adapting to the situation.

Additionally, Mustapha (2022) revealed in his study that because of verbal punishment, learners take this as a challenge and develop oppositional motivation which was indicated by Rain in the present study in which he stated, "*I want to prove that I'm not like that, that I am more than that.*"

Finally, Rodrigo-Ruiz (2016) found out in her study that the reason as to why Borbs indicated "*In a way, when the verbal punishments from my teachers really sunk in, I actually used it as motivation to strive harder in my science studies.*" was because when the student must be corrected, negative emotions can cause positive effects.

In the present study, students had mentioned that they also had a negative perceived influence of verbal punishment to their science learning. As shown in Table 5, they indicated that the verbal punishments they experienced led them to do their requirements for the sake of submission, question their own capabilities, retaliate in order

to get back to their teacher, caused them to be demotivated, and have a poor performance in science.

Table 5

Negative Perceived Influence of Verbal Punishment

Themes	Subthemes	Students' Response
Doing requirements for the sake of submission	Finishing requirements to 'survive' in class	"I reached a point where I'm really lazy to do the activities; I do it on the same day as my deadline. Now, I'm just surviving in class." (Rain)
	Blind Compliance	"But honestly speaking, it's like you're just doing it for the sake of compliance." (Ariel)
Questioning one's capability	Self-Diffidence	"It really stuck in my mind and there were times that I really succumbed and thought that "I am not good enough, what am I doing here" (Ariel)
	Gaslighting oneself	"I'll just stay here. I won't join the group activities for now because I'm clumsy." (Aloysius)
Poor Science Performance	Difficulty on focusing on studying	"The course is already difficult, and then you add that, I found it hard to focus." (Zebra)
	Feelings were hurt which caused bad grades	"I got offended. I think my grades went down then. My grades in science went down because the teacher was rude to me." (Katropa)
Demotivated	Laziness	"It is degrading to the point that you will be too lazy to study the things you should study from him/her." (Bryle)
	Loss of interest in learning	"My interest in learning disappeared." (Katropa)

Retaliation	Getting back at the teacher	"You'll belittle me, and then I'll humiliate you. It's like getting even." (Senyorpickels)
	Talking back	"I answered my professor back then with 'TH' (a snide response to being suspected)" (Lei)

Most literature was clearly stating the negative effects of verbal punishment towards students' science learning. According to Botazzi et al. (2016), verbal punishment has a direct impact on students' self-esteem, and this seems to be the reason as to why Ariel questioned herself when she was interviewed in the present study, and stated that *"I am not good enough, what am I doing here"*

Additionally, the study of Mahmood (2015) revealed that the learning environment is very important for students' learning, and anything that may happen inside the students' learning environment may affect the student's performance. This was shown when Zebra said that *"I had difficulty focusing"* during his interview. Thus, the present study posits that his difficulty in focusing brought by the verbal punishment that he experienced from his teacher resulted in his poor performance in science.

Furthermore, in the present study, Lei displayed retaliation after experiencing verbal punishments from his teacher by saying *"I answered my professor back then with 'TH' (a snide response to being suspected)*. His action matches the findings of the study of Bahou, and Zakharia (2019). They were able to report that students who talk back to their teachers are activating their agencies, because they consider it as their unassailable right. Based on their findings, it is a possible reason as to why Lei retaliated against his teacher.

Also, it seems to be that the indication of students in the present study of why they were just doing requirements for the sake of submission was reported by Tus (2020). Based on his findings, the respondents in his research had an average level of perception towards the delay avoidance, and work methods that denoted their promptness in accomplishing academic requirements. This could be a reason why Rain indicated *"I reached a point where I'm too lazy to do the activities; I do it on the same day as my deadline. Now, I'm just surviving in class."*

Lastly, according to Lopez and Tun (2017), the feedback that the students received from their teachers can either motivate or demotivate them. In their study, they reported that the participants felt demotivated when they were given feedback individually, due to fear of mockery, or criticism which can be seen in front of the whole class. This could also be a reason why in the present study, Bryle mentioned *"It is degrading to the point that you will be lazy to study the things you should study from him/her."*

Conclusions

Given the findings of the present study, the researchers make the following conclusions:

1. The most common types of verbal punishment experienced by the college students in NCR are accusation, name-calling, reprimanding, shaming, and belittling.

2. College students from the NCR experienced verbal punishment one (1) to two (2) times per week inside the science classroom.

3. Freshman students experienced all the different types of verbal punishment never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.24. The Sophomores experienced name-calling, shaming, belittling, blaming, and reprimanding sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week and accusation and humiliation never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.59. For the Juniors, they experienced Verbal Punishment experienced accusation, shaming, and belittling, blaming and reprimanding sometimes or one (1) to two (2) times per week and name-calling, blaming, reprimanding and humiliation never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.47. Lastly, the Seniors experienced all the different types of verbal punishment never or zero (0) times per week with an average of 1.33.

4. The perceived influences of verbal punishment on students' science learning were positive, and negative in nature. Students had mentioned that verbal punishments had a positive perceived influence on their science learning, because it encouraged them to do better, it became an opportunity for self-improvement, led them to be dependent on themselves, and used it as a driving factor to change the teacher's perspective towards them. On the other hand, students had indicated that the verbal punishments they experienced led them to do their requirements for the sake of submission, question their own capabilities, retaliate in order to get back to their teacher, cause them to be demotivated, and have a poor performance in science.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of this study, the researchers would like to make some recommendations:

1. Develop a tool that assesses the authenticity of verbal punishment experiences and a scale that measures that what they have experienced is indeed verbal punishment.
2. Have the students a daily journal where they can take note/reflect whenever they have experienced verbal punishment by their teacher throughout the duration of the study.

3. Formulate an instrument for an in-depth study, and reporting of verbal punishment per year level.
4. Make use of alternative methods of data collection such as non-graded reflections and information from guidance offices. Furthermore, if future research would include recorded videos of teacher-to-student verbal punishment from classrooms that have CCTV cameras with built-in microphones, these authentic data would further strengthen the need to research verbal punishment inside classrooms.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers strongly adhered to ethical standards to ensure the integrity of all participants involved. Participants were fully informed about the research's purpose, and procedures to ensure transparency. Research participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement, and their privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the study.

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